

**RISK OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE IN PATIENTS
WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS****Soliyeva Shakhnozaxon Bakhtiyorjonovna****Andijan State Medical Institute****Shagzatova Barno Khabibullaevna****Professor at the Department of Internal Medicine No. 2,
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18858241>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 26th February 2026Accepted: 27th February 2026Online: 28th February 2026**KEYWORDS**

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ABSTRACT

It is well known that the treatment of diabetes is a continuous and uninterrupted process, and in this regard, treatment methods are evolving thanks to changes in the healthcare system and treatment strategies, as well as the emergence of new knowledge.

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The incidence of diabetes has been steadily increasing over the last decade. The prevalence of this disease has risen so sharply in recent decades that it is now considered an epidemic. Diabetes mellitus currently accounts for 5–13% of total healthcare expenditure worldwide. Diabetes mellitus is a chronic disease characterised by an elevated blood glucose level, which can shorten patients' life expectancy by up to 10 years, up to 75% of people die from cardiovascular diseases. To reduce the risk of diabetes, it is also important to engage in regular physical activity, as well as, it is important to maintain a healthy lifestyle by adopting a healthy diet and controlling body mass index. The most important goals of treatment are to prevent cardiovascular diseases by keeping blood sugar levels as close to normal as possible, as well as reducing the risk of developing microvascular complications, such as those associated with diabetic retinopathy, neuropathy, and nephropathy. Current methods for treating diabetes mellitus

1. Agents that reduce insulin resistance.
2. Agents that act on pancreatic beta-cells to enhance insulin production.
3. Agents that inhibit the absorption of glucose from the diet.
4. Insulin and insulin analogues.

One of the substances that has been used for many years in the treatment of diabetes mellitus is metformin and sulfonylurea preparations. The latter group of drugs includes agonists of glucagon-like peptide-1 receptors and dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitors. Glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists are currently used in combination with dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors, as their combined effects complement each other.

In patients with diabetes mellitus, intolerance to and adverse effects of antidiabetic agents during hypoglycaemic episodes are observed. Therefore, in conclusion, it should be noted that many synthetic drugs directly affect the liver's metabolic processes, cardiovascular diseases, the presence of side effects when using them in patients with kidney failure increases the need to use herbal products.

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